

Ethical considerations of open science in qualitative research

The Ethical Committee for Social Sciences and Humanities (EA SHW)

**Universiteit
Antwerpen**

Presented By
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Chair EASHW

Anonymised case text

Publishers are seeing **an increase in** submitted data generated from **qualitative research studies**. These studies are answering important questions such as identifying unmet need or highlighting the lived experience, potentially adding real value to the body of evidence especially in rare diseases. They are often Pharma funded and / or patient advocacy group led.

Many of these studies have been conducted compliantly in accordance with the EPHMRA guidelines, which state that Ethics committee approval is not required if studies meet the criteria of market research. In addition, these studies are non-interventional and the Health Research Authority tool also indicates that Ethics committee approval is NOT required.

However, our interpretation of the **COPE guidelines** is that ethics committee **approval should be provided for all studies involving humans**. This potential disconnect is frustrating for potential authors as is often not identified until after the study has been performed and is ready for publication. Furthermore, there does seem to be some inconsistency in the published literature, with some such studies being published without ethics approval.

Further clarity from publishers regarding when Ethics approval is required for non-interventional questionnaire-based market research studies, and alignment with the existing market research guidelines, would be welcome to ensure that these important qualitative research data are reported. Publication of such studies may highlight important aspects of rare disease and prevent repetition of similar studies in often limited populations. **The need to submit to an Ethics board unnecessarily is costly and can be a real barrier to non-HCP led research** (e.g. patient-led research) who do not have access.

Doing no harm is a basic ethical principle

BUT different people interpret the meaning of 'harm' differently and may also perceive it differently at different moments in time.

As researchers, we must ensure we do not make malicious use of information, and that we do not exploit (the honesty or vulnerability of) the person we have invited to participate in our study.

EASHW

EASHW is there for

- **Participants**

- Right to full information
- Voluntary participation at all times
- Special attention to young and vulnerable populations

AND

- **Researchers**

- Right to conduct research,
- Right to do so safely,
- Right to retain data after collection with informed consent,
- Special attention for young/inexperienced researchers

EASHW TIP SHEETS

Online via WEBSITE

[https://www.uantwerpen.be/nl/onderzoek/b
eleid/evaluatie-ethiek-integriteit/ethische-
advisering/shw/](https://www.uantwerpen.be/nl/onderzoek/b
eleid/evaluatie-ethiek-integriteit/ethische-
advisering/shw/)

Or

[https://www.uantwerpen.be/en/research/pol
icy/assessment-ethics-integrity/ethics-
screening/eashw/](https://www.uantwerpen.be/en/research/pol
icy/assessment-ethics-integrity/ethics-
screening/eashw/)

In ethical research,
nothing is forbidden —
but *everything*
demands reflection.

No study is too complex for ethical approval,
only too important to bypass it.

Part C of the application – 17 questions

RISK

C1- BRIEFLY DESCRIBE (A) THE INTENDED STUDY DESIGN and (b) THE STUDY POPULATION(S).

For **A**: What type of research is being conducted? Are there multiple studies/methods? Briefly describe them. Are there multiple phases in the research? Provide a short description. The explanation should be **very SHORT and CLEAR**, even for those with no prior experience in this type of research.

For **B**: Indicate (1) the estimated number of participants, (2) the inclusion/exclusion criteria, and (3) the recruitment method.

Qualitative studies often involve small, specific, and **context-rich samples**.

→ *CAN anonymity (= no re-identification is possible) be guaranteed?*

Openly sharing this data increases re-identification risks, even when names are removed.

Non-anonymity is not the problem, rather:

How can and will you maximally (1) inform and (2) protect participants?

Consent forms enable participants to formally decide whether or not they want to participate voluntarily in the study and oblige researchers to ensure that everyone involved fully understands the process.

C - 2 & 3

INFORMATION AND CONSENT

Q2. ETHICAL CONSENT: DO YOU DEVIATE FROM ACTIVE WRITTEN "INFORMED CONSENT" OF ALL PARTICIPANTS?

Basic premise of good conduct

Preferably written, if you deviate from this, this must be justified.

Q3. LEGAL CONSENT: DO YOU COLLECT OR USE DATA THAT IDENTIFIES INDIVIDUALS BEFORE, DURING OR AFTER THE STUDY?

GDPR legislation applies,

Written consent, if you deviate: keep track of names in a separate file

PRIVACY COMMITTEE

Qualitative researchers often ideally rely on oral and/or nuanced, *evolving* consent (e.g. in ethnography or narrative interviews)

→ *EASHW: Ok when motivated*

→ *PRIVACY: may require "Public Interest" as legal ground*

Evolving Consent in qualitative research

“Normally” informed consent is obtained only **at the start of the study**

BUT this process is particularly complex in qualitative research which is mostly emergent in nature.

THUS

It might be useful to work with “**Process/Rolling/Provisional Informed Consent**”

= informed consent given once the **study is underway** and new, unexpected issues that were not foreseen in the initial document arise and need to be negotiated.

→ You could add these as “changes to an existing file” to EASHW

I Agree

PART C -4

IDENTIFIABILITY

Q4. IDENTIFIABILITY IN RESEARCH

RESULTS: CAN PEOPLE BE IDENTIFIED OR RE-IDENTIFIED IN THE ANALYSIS DATA AND/OR RESULTS?

ANONYMOUS \neq PSEUDONYMOUS

Pseudonymize data

DIFFERENT CARRIERS

Anonymize data

If you claim your data are anonymous, then NO ONE* — not you, not your team, not future researchers — can EVER identify a participant again. Not now. Not later. Not ever.

* “No one” refers to individuals with average knowledge and resources. Data scientists, state actors, or intelligence services may still be able to re-identify.

**... which is precisely why data must be treated with extreme caution if truly sensitive or in unsafe contexts...

Qualitative researchers face a dilemma: how to convey **detailed and accurate** information about the social world they are exploring, while **at the same time protecting participants' identities?**

People sometimes feel identified and hurt by research reports. Pseudonyms and 'camouflaged' descriptions are often recognised by participants, their family members or those outside the process who read the study.

-
- NEVER promise what you cannot guarantee.
 - Be TRANSPARENT

PART C -4

IDENTIFIABILITY

Q4. IDENTIFIABILITY IN RESEARCH RESULTS: CAN PEOPLE BE IDENTIFIED OR RE-IDENTIFIED IN THE ANALYSIS DATA AND/OR RESULTS?

Pain point?

In-depth qualitative **quotes are often highly personal and context-bound.**

Even with pseudonyms, participants can be easily re-identified — especially in small communities or rare roles.

Requires (extra) ethical reflection

Non-anonymity is not the problem, rather: How can and will you maximally (1) inform and (2) protect participants?

Which data are participants allowed to view?

Identity

RESPONDENTS CAN
VIEW/CHANGE/DELETE
THIS

Non identifiable data

NOT THIS

Full Data

NOT THIS

Protect yourself as a researcher; once they agree to participate after FULL INFORMATION and COMPLETE withdrawal, retracting data from the study is not an option. ! DURING the study, revocation and loss of data is POSSIBLE.

PART C -4

IDENTIFIABILITY

Q4. IDENTIFIABILITY IN RESEARCH RESULTS: CAN PEOPLE BE IDENTIFIED OR RE-IDENTIFIED IN THE ANALYSIS DATA AND/OR RESULTS?

Non-anonymity CAN become a problem, if participants withdraw their data at later points in time.

Is this possible??

See <https://publicationethics.org/>

Case ⓘ

Share ↗

Withdrawal of acceptance based on potentially unconsented data

- Advice from COPE Council ⓘ

Two papers were retracted (without dispute from the authors) after a lengthy investigation.

Research ethics

Case number: 20-27

Case year: 2020

Case status: Closed

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PART C -4

IDENTIFIABILITY

Q4. IDENTIFIABILITY IN RESEARCH RESULTS: CAN PEOPLE BE IDENTIFIED OR RE-IDENTIFIED IN THE ANALYSIS DATA AND/OR RESULTS?

Non-anonymity CAN become a problem, if participants withdraw their data at later points in time.

- **Make things crystal clear in the consent process**
 - Exact aim of your study, 100% transparency
 - Include that withdrawal may only be possible **up to a certain point.**
 - Check with Legal Office

*“You may withdraw your data at any point **before publication.** After that, removal may no longer be possible.”*

If quotes will be published with names, **participants must give separate explicit consent.**

- Ask consent again, let them read the quotes

SECTION C -5 & 6

Reimbursements for participation

Q5. REIMBURSEMENT: DO YOU OFFER REIMBURSEMENT OR EXTRAS THAT MAY POSE ETHICAL RISKS?

Q6. COMPENSATION: DO YOU COLLECT CONTACT INFORMATION FOR PARTICIPANT COMPENSATION THAT CAN BE LINKED TO THE RESEARCH DATA?

No extra/special aspects here?

PART C – 7 & 8

Research with minors

7. AGE + NON-ANONYMOUS: DO YOU DEVIATE FROM THE WRITTEN CONSENT OF (1) MINORS (<18) AND (2) THEIR PARENT/GUARDIAN?

active consent from (BOTH?) parents/ a guardian is required in this case.

8. AGE + FULLY ANONYMOUS: DO YOU DEVIATE FROM WRITTEN CONSENT FROM (1) PARTICIPANTS UNDER THE AGE OF 13 AND (2) THEIR PARENT/GUARDIAN?

Qualitative studies with minors are rich in data but carry higher risk.

Publishing full transcripts or excerpts, even anonymously but with the potential of re-identification, *may breach ethical and legal norms without dual parental + child consent.*

PART C – 7 & 8

Research with minors

Under Belgian Civil Code Articles 373 & 374, parental authority is generally **exercised jointly by both parents**, even if they're separated.

In practice, each parent is presumed to act with the consent of the other *unless a court has ruled otherwise*.

BUT ethics committees **encourage** dual-parent consent to:

- Reduce risk of disputes later
- Respect the principle of *shared parental authority*
- Protect rights of absent parent
- Uphold public trust

You don't always need both signatures.

But you should always try.

→ Document your efforts and check for sole custody or legal objections.

If one parent objects, you cannot proceed ethically.

PART C – 7 & 8

Research with minors

What if the minor WANTS to participate, but the parent(s) DO NOT WANT their child to participate?

GDRP – **Common Interest**
Privacy@UAntwerpen.be

Age of 13

In certain cases, seeking parental consent — or even informing parents — may not be advised, as it could prevent some minors from participating in the research. This applies particularly to studies involving sensitive topics where requiring parental involvement could pose risks to the minor's safety, privacy, or autonomy

Anonymised case text

As editor of a psychology journal, I received a manuscript from a group of scholars. The authors describe a qualitative online study with **adolescent girls, aged 15–18 years**, who met in person with a stranger they first 'met' online. The girls describe their reasoning about the risks, the safety measures they used and reactions to discomfort they experienced in the meetings.

The authors noted on our required information form that they "Confirm that all the research meets the ethical guidelines, including adherence to the legal requirements of the study country." They also note in their cover letter that the paper conforms to APA (American Psychological Association) standards.

In the paper, the authors note that "**parental consent was not required**" because "all of the participants were older than 15 at the time of the interview, which is the legal age in the country where the study was performed".

Because they identified the source of a number of quotations from the interviews that they conducted as being from 15 year olds, I contacted the first author for clarification. I also asked where the statute is listed that states 15 years as the age of consent in that country and also asked if the study was reviewed by an ethical review board.

Advice

Advice from COPE Members: Advice on this case is from COPE Members and COPE Council Members. Advice on individual cases is not formal COPE guidance.

The Forum suggested there are two issues here: the age of legal consent without parental approval and the ethical issue.

While the study has institutional backing, some of the Forum were of the opinion that the study **should have been reviewed by an institutional review board.** Only an institutional review board or an ethical board can judge whether or not consent should have been obtained.

One view was that parents should have been informed for the younger aged participants (15 and 16 year olds). However, another view was that the **benefits outweigh the risks,** and that if the parents had been informed, that may have **prevented the participants taking part in the study.** The age of consent varies widely in different countries. If participants are over the age of consent for that particular country and the study was done according to national standards, then the authors should be allowed to publish. A suggestion was that if the paper is accepted for publication, the editor could put a statement or note on the paper around the issue of consent, in the cultural context. It may also be useful for the editor to write an editorial comment as readers may also have similar questions.

Since many journals have international authors, should the onus be on editors if there is lack of clarity to confirm the norms elsewhere. **Do we need universal standards for issues like this?**

PART C – 7 & 8

Research with minors

Never forget the child's consent

It is necessary to design age and capacity-appropriate consent mechanisms. These mechanisms could be **more graphic** and present the information in such a way as to **guarantee that the child in question understands what they are committing to** by agreeing to participate in the process.

Be sensitive to young children's signs of **dissent to participate**. **Researchers need to obtain children's true consent to participate** in the research project, rather than just the consent of their parents or guardians, as some studies do.

PART C – 7 & 8

Research with minors

Your position as a researcher

Address potential **power imbalances between researchers and those being researched.**

“**ethical symmetry**”: researchers should adopt a methodological attitude that recognises, respects and incorporates the active involvement of infants in research processes.

Also for research with (+18) students!!!

C 9/10

Vulnerability

9. VULNERABLE PARTICIPANTS: DO YOU WORK WITH VERY VULNERABLE PARTICIPANTS (VERY VULNERABLE PRIOR TO THE STUDY)?

10. MORE VULNERABLE THROUGH PARTICIPATION: DO PARTICIPANTS BECOME (MORE) VULNERABLE THROUGH PARTICIPATION IN THE STUDY?

Open science is fundamentally at odds with *research involving people in distress, trauma, dependency or legal uncertainty.*

If full anonymization is impossible; *can data sharing be ethical ?*

Once shared openly, *the impact is not reversible* — data could resurface in future contexts beyond researcher control.

Vulnerability comes with greater ethical responsibility

Anonymised case text

A study was submitted that reported the prevalence of an intestinal infection in a tribal community. The authors did not obtain informed individual consent for stool collection from the study participants; instead they obtained consent from the leaders of each village. The study protocol was approved by the national IRB, but the protocol made no specific mention of stool collection—it referred to a study of a respiratory infection and “interdisciplinary research”, so we are unclear if the IRB knew that such collection would take place. The authors had obtained a permit for research from the country’s “national foundation”.

The handling editors, who work in the country in which this study took place, and who are very familiar with the national laws on conducting health research in tribal communities, state that:

- (1) The law makes it clear that while obtaining prior consent from community leaders is very good practice, it should not dispense with efforts to obtain individual consent.
- (2) Every individual must give consent; illiterate individuals should give a digital print.

We wrote to the authors to ask why they did not obtain individual consent, and whether the national IRB had approved the stool collection. We asked to see the protocol approved by the IRB.

They explained that they had published nine papers arising from this work, no journal had ever questioned them on ethical oversight (or asked to see the study protocol) and they are the only doctors to have ever offered this tribe any medical treatment. They withdrew their paper in protest.

Anonymised case text

A paper on a vulnerable population was published in a journal. The journal followed their usual procedures for processing papers on vulnerable populations, by requesting and reviewing further information on the ethics approval and consent procedures of the study (eg, recruitment procedures; blank version of the consent document participants read and signed; the study protocol that was approved; ethics approval certificate).

However, the paper published individual profiles (Short Tandem Repeat (STR)) which contained genetic data from the participants. A reader contacted the journal, highlighting that these data are identifiable and could pose a risk to the vulnerable participants in the study. The publisher was not previously aware of this, and after discussions with the editors the journal asked the authors to remove those data.

This prompted a wider discussion about data availability for manuscripts on vulnerable populations, and whether it is ethical to encourage data availability for such papers even when written informed consent for its publication was obtained from participants. There is growing concern in the media regarding the welfare of some vulnerable populations and an increasing pressure to protect those participants in research. The publisher is keen to do everything it can to protect vulnerable populations, and would therefore benefit greatly from COPE's advice on the following three questions.

2022 case

Best practices

- **Working WITH rather than ON participants,**
 - Co-design the research WITH these groups, be open to novel methodologies
 - biographical-narrative research or action research allow to change the traditional power structure and developing more democratic research processes
 - Likewise, in-depth interviews, photo-elicitation or lifelines are instruments that involve the participants in the studies by giving them a voice and making them co-protagonists of the research processes

PART C – 12 RECORDINGS

Q12. RECORDINGS: DO YOU MAKE OR COLLECT RECORDINGS WITH IDENTITY INFORMATION OF PEOPLE, AND DO YOU SAVE THEM DURING OR AFTER THE DATA ANALYSIS?

Note: This also applies to all types of recordings with (in)direct identity information. This also applies to recordings that participants provide themselves (such as in photovoice research). If supplied materials contain recognizable people, answer yes here.

Read the tips on recordings on the EASHW website, don't miss this step!

Recordings are often essential in qualitative research, but they are ***by nature identifiable.***

Long-term storage or sharing (even for replication purposes) requires **fourfold explicit and separate consent:** to record, store, share, and publish.

13. DECEPTION: DO YOU MISLEAD PARTICIPANTS WITHOUT FURTHER EXPLANATION AND THE RIGHT TO WITHDRAW AFTERWARDS?

Sample debrief form can be found in Tip Sheets

While rare in qualitative research, some ethnography or disguised observation may involve deception.

Any undisclosed recording or unconsented data use is incompatible with open sharing norms.

PART C – 14 & 15 Reuse of data

14. (RE)USE OF EXISTING DATA: DO YOU USE EXISTING NON-ANONYMOUS DATA WITHOUT THE ORIGINAL CONSENT OF THE PARTICIPANT(S)?

15. LATER REUSE OF COLLECTED DATA: WILL YOU USE NON-ANONYMOUS DATA FOR **OTHER PURPOSES** LATER?

- *For anonymous data, a standard notification in the informed consent forms is sufficient.*
- *For non-anonymous data, according to the GDPR legislation, you must indicate in detail what you share/will share with whom.*

For non-anonymous data:

“your data may be reused for future scientific studies”

→ This does *not* satisfy GDPR : **you need named, concrete purposes** *or re-consent participants before sharing.*

Why not obtain a general open consent for “scientific research purposes” for non-anonymous data?

Havasupai Tribe v. Arizona Board of Regents (USA)

Original study: DNA samples were collected from members of the Havasupai Tribe under consent for diabetes research.

Later re-use: the samples were re-used for schizophrenia studies, ancestry/migration, etc., without tribe members' consent for those uses.

- This is a classic example of **data repurposing** beyond original consent, albeit in biomedical/genetic research, but...
- ...it illustrates *how participants may feel betrayed* when data is used for entirely different research aims.

Mental health interviews

Original aim: interviews about depression in young adults

Repurposed for: Research about AI model training for
“emotional surveillance” in hiring tools

Ethnography in a religious community

Original research aim: Understanding how young adults find meaning in small faith-based groups

Repurposed for: A study analyzing “radicalization potential” in religious young adults

Can participants feel betrayed when
data is used for entirely different
research aims?

16. DOES THE RESEARCH TAKE PLACE IN (OR WITH COMMUNITIES FROM) CONTEXTS OF *INEQUALITY OR HISTORICAL OPPRESSION*?

In structurally oppressed contexts, data sharing can become data extraction.

Co-develop open science plans with local researchers or community representatives

Check local legislations!!

AND

Follow **ethical frameworks developed by communities themselves** that define how data *about them* should be handled.

Offer local veto power over publication or reuse

- You may need to **pause or cancel publication** if the community raises concerns.
- **Example:** Participants later ask to restrict access to certain interviews because of new political tensions. You **honor that request.**

Q16 is about “**Relational Ethics**”

= the implicit and explicit contracts established (1) between researchers (2) research participants and (3) all other parties involved.

The implicit contract is linked to the personal relationship between the parties, which (further) develops as the study progresses.

Within this relationship, the following questions need to be considered: How does the other party feel? Is the research relationship characterized by mutual respect, care and interdependence, as opposed to distance or hierarchy?

Aim to not to acknowledge the others and take their perspective into account. Particularly important when working with vulnerable groups, power imbalances etc.

Applying an interdependence theory lens to your project

Six key dimensions

“How is your relationship with RESEARCHERS / PARTICIPANTS / OTHER PARTIES”

1. **Level of dependence** of people: *How much* does a person rely on others?
2. **Mutuality** of dependence: is there a power imbalance?
3. **Basis of dependence**: can a person control their own outcomes independently (individual control), or is a person fully (other control) or partially (joint control) dependent on other people's actions?
4. **Alignment of interests**: Do a person's goals align with the goals of others, or do they conflict? It is also important to know whether people can trust each other('s interests) or not.
5. **Temporal structure of relations** must be considered. - Past experiences with others influence how we navigate life today. Whether we foresee a future together or not, and how intensely we see each other connected in that future influences how we interact with each other.
6. **Information (un)certainty**: we often do not know what the intentions of others really are. This uncertainty can lead to suspicion or misunderstandings, while clarity fosters trust.

If you want to act ethically, you need to address these questions

17. ARE THERE ANY ETHICAL RISKS DURING THE RESEARCH THAT HAVE NOT YET BEEN MENTIONED? And/or DO YOU HAVE ANY FURTHER QUESTIONS FOR THE COMMITTEE?

Researchers can (must) self-identify grey zones like “incidental findings” (legal issues!), “embarrassment risk” “potential misinterpretation” and so on

Incidental findings!!

Sometimes, participants say things that researchers may wish they had not said...

Legal consequences? Contact the Legal Affairs Office, even when in doubt!

2 ethical dilemmas

- 1. Should we publish** declarations that we think may harm participants, **even when we have their consent to do so?**
- 2. And should we include pejorative comments about third parties** named by participants?
 - What should we do, for example, with hurtful comments made by participants about other people?

In ethical research,
nothing is forbidden —
but *everything*
demands reflection.

Open science in qualitative work = case-by-
case dilemmas that require careful handling

EASHW encourages a culture of **early reflection**, consultation and “better be safe than sorry”.

Application Timeline

Start Application

Start of the Study

**TIME TO
PREPARE**

MINIMUM
1 DAY

**+/-14
DAYS**

MINOR REVISIONS
MAJOR REVISIONS